

Some Studies on Iodo- and Acylflavones*

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7-Methoxy-6-Iodo 7,4'-dimethoxy-6-Iodo and 6-methoxy-5-Iodoflavone have been converted into the corresponding biflavonyl and cyanoflavone derivatives respectively. The structures of the cyano derivatives were proved by alkaline hydrolysis to the known cyano acids. Further Beckmann rearrangements of the oximes of 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl and 7-hydroxy-8-benzoylflavone have been carried out and the structures of the amid derivatives were proved by comparing the amino derivatives obtained from the amid derivatives by hydrolysis and from the known nitro flavones by reduction.

The earlier work on the synthesis of cyanoflavones¹ and biflavonyl derivatives² iodoflavones done in this laboratory has been extended and some new cyanoflavone biflavonyl derivatives have been synthesised. Further, Beckmann rearrangement of oximes of some acylflavones has been studied.

7-Methoxy-6-iodo-, 7,4'-dimethoxy-6-iodo and 6-methoxy-5-iodoflavone which prepared previously³ when subjected to Ullmann re-action with copper bronze gave 7,4'-dimethoxy-6,6"-biflavonyl, 7,7",4',4'''-tetramethoxy-6,6"-biflavonyl and 6,6"-dimethoxy biflavonyl respectively. Further, the crossed Ullmann reaction between the above derivatives and iodo benzene have been carried out and the corresponding 6- and 5-p derivatives were synthesised.

7-Methoxy-6-iodoflavone on fusion with cuprous cyanide gave the 6-cyano derivative which on alkaline hydrolysis gave the known 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-cyanobenzoic acid. On hydrolysis with 70% sulphuric acid it gave 7-hydroxyflavone-6-carboxylic acid⁴ prepared earlier by Shah and Sethna by a different method. 7,4'-Dimethoxy-6-iodoflavone on a similar treatment gave the 6-cyano derivative which on alkaline hydrolysis gave 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-cyanobenzoic acid¹ and with 70% sulphuric acid it gave 7-hydroxy-4'-methoxyflavone-6-carboxylic acid which on decarboxylation gave 7-hydroxy-4'-methoxyflavone.

6-Methoxy-5-iodoflavone in reaction with cuprous cyanide gave the 5-cyano derivative which on heating on a steam bath with 50% sulphuric acid gave 6-methoxyflavone-5-carboxylic acid but on refluxing with 50% sulphuric acid gave 6-hydroxyflavone. 6-Methoxy-5-iodoflavone on alkaline hydrolysis gave a keto acid to which 2-acetyl-3-hydroxy-6-methoxybenzoic acid structure is assigned. On heating with aluminium chloride it gave quinone phenone. Sugawara⁶ carried out the Beckmann rearrangement of the oximes of 5-hydroxy-6-acetylflavone with phosphoryl chlorides and obtained 5-hydroxy-6-aminoflavone.

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In the present work the oximes of 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl and 7-hydroxy-8-benzoylflavone⁴ on Beckmann rearrangement gave the 8-acetamido and 8-benzamido derivatives respectively. These on hydrolysis with sulphuric acid gave 7-hydroxy-8-aminoflavone as seen by direct comparison with the product obtained on reduction of the known 7-hydroxy-8-nitroflavone⁵ with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid.

The oxime of 7-hydroxy-8-formyl and 7-methoxy-8-formylflavones on heating with phosphoryl chloride gave the known 8-cyano derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL*

7,7''-Dimethoxy-6,6''-biflavonyl : 7-Methoxy-6-iodoflavone (3.78 g.) in diphenyl ether (20 ml.) was refluxed with copper bronze (1.89 g.) and a trace of iodine for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the filtrate diluted with petroleum ether (40–60°). The solid obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 337°.

The same biflavonyl derivative was obtained by heating the iodoflavone (3.78 g.) with copper bronze (1.89 g.) without any solvent in an oil bath for 10 mins. at 240–50°. (Found : C, 75.94; H, 4.84. $C_{32}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 76.49; H, 4.38%.)

7,7',4',4'''-Tetramethoxy-6,6''-biflavonyl : A mixture of 7,4'-dimethoxy-6-iodoflavone (3.96 g.) and copper bronze (1.89 g.) was inserted in a previously heated oil bath at 240–50° and kept for 10 mins. with occasional stirring. The brown reaction mixture was extracted with acetic acid. The extracts on dilution with water gave a product which crystallised from acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 326°. (Found : C, 72.53; H, 4.53; $C_{34}H_{26}O_8$ requires C, 72.61; H, 4.63%.)

6,6''-Dimethoxy-5,5''-biflavonyl : A mixture of 6-methoxy-5-iodoflavone (3.78 g.) and copper bronze (1.89 g.) in diphenyl ether (10 ml.) was refluxed for 1 hr. The product obtained on working up the reaction mixture as before was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 336°. The same product was also obtained without using the diphenyl ether as a solvent. (Found : C, 76.48; H, 4.50, $C_{32}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 76.49; H, 4.38%.)

7-Methoxy-6-phenylflavone : 7-Methoxy-6-iodoflavone (3.16 g.) intimately mixed with copper bronze (4.40 g.) and iodobenzene (4.14 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 250° for 1 hr. with occasional shaking. The reaction mixture was then extracted with cold petroleum ether to remove unreacted iodo benzene and biphenyl. The residue was repeatedly extracted with hot benzene and petroleum ether mixture (1 : 1). 7,7''-Dimethoxy-6,6''-biflavonyl described above was obtained from the residue. The benzene petroleum ether extract on cooling gave 7-methoxy-6-phenylflavone. It crystallised from benzene in shining needles, m.p. 161°. (Found : C, 80.40; H, 4.94. $C_{22}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 80.48; H, 4.88%). 7-Methoxyflavone was recovered from the benzene petroleum ether extract after removal of 7-methoxy-6-phenylflavone.

7,4'-Dimethoxy-6-phenylflavone : A mixture of 7,4'-dimethoxy-6-iodoflavone (3.20 g.), copper bronze (4.40 g.) and iodobenzene (4.14 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 250° for 1 hr. with occasional shaking and the reaction mixture extracted with cold petroleum ether to

* All the m.ps. are uncorrected.

remove unreacted iodobenzene and biphenyl and then with hot benzene and petroleum ether mixture (1 : 1) to remove 7,4'-dimethoxyflavone. The residue was then extracted with hot benzene which gave 7,4'-dimethoxy-6-phenylflavone. It crystallised from dilute acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 200°. (Found : C, 77.02; H, 5.43. $C_{23}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 77.09; H, 5.03%). The residue after benzene extract gave 7,7'',4,4'''-tetramethoxy-6,6''-biflavonyl described above.

6-Methoxy-5-phenylflavone : A mixture of 6-methoxy-5-iodoflavone (3.16 g.), copper bronze (4.40 g.) and iodobenzene (4.14 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 250° for 1 hr. and then washed with cold petroleum ether and then extracted with hot benzene and petroleum ether mixture (1 : 1). 6,6''-Dimethoxy-5,5''-biflavonyl described above was obtained from the residue. The combined extracts on cooling gave 6-methoxy-5-phenylflavone. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 223°. (Found : C, 80.48; H, 5.08. $C_{22}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 80.48; H, 4.88%). 6-Methoxyflavone was recovered from the benzene petroleum ether mixture after separation of 6-methoxy-5-phenylflavone.

7-Methoxy-6-cyanoflavone : 7-Methoxy-6-iodoflavone (3.78 g.) intimately mixed with cuprous cyanide (1.78 g.) and copper sulphate (0.25 g.) was heated at 220–25° for 10 mins and then extracted with hot acetone. The extracts on concentration gave 7-Methoxy-6-cyanoflavone. It crystallised from ethyl alcohol in needles, m.p. 227°. Shah and Sethna¹ prepared the same compound by a different method and reported the same m.p. (Found : C, 73.79; H, 4.02; N, 4.92. $C_{17}H_{11}O_3N$ requires : C, 73.64; H, 4.00; N, 5.05%).

Hydrolysis : 7-Methoxy-6-cyanoflavone (0.5 g.) was heated with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (10%, 20 ml.) on a steam bath for 2 hr. The product obtained on acidification crystallised from alcohol. M.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-cyanobenzoic acid prepared according to Shah and Sethna¹ was 232–33°.

7-Hydroxyflavone-6-carboxylic acid : 7-Methoxy-6-cyanoflavone (0.7 g.) was heated with sulphuric acid (70%, 25 ml.) under gentle reflux for 3 hrs. The reaction mixture was then added to crushed ice and the product extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution. The product obtained on acidification of this extract was crystallised from ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 311°. (Found : C, 67.88; H, 3.67. $C_{16}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 68.08; H, 3.57%).

7,4'-Dimethoxy-6-cyanoflavone : An intimate mixture of 7,4'-dimethoxy-6-iodoflavone (4.08 g.), cuprous cyanide (1.78 g.) and copper sulphate (0.25 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 220–25° for 10 mins and then extracted with hot acetone. The product obtained on removal of acetone was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 244°. (Found : C, 70.65; H, 4.05; N, 4.65. $C_{18}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 70.35; H, 4.26; N, 4.56%).

Hydrolysis : 7,4'-Dimethoxy-6-cyanoflavone (0.5 g.) was hydrolysed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (10%, 20 ml.) as described earlier. The product obtained crystallised from alcohol. The m.p. and mixed m.p. with 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-cyanobenzoic acid prepared according to Shah and Sethna¹ was not depressed.

7-Hydroxy-4'-methoxyflavone-6-carboxylic acid : 7,4'-Dimethoxy-6-cyanoflavone was hydrolysed with sulphuric acid (70%, 25 ml.) as described earlier and the product tallised from ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 319–20° (decomp. efferv.). Its solution gave red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 65.89; H, C₁₇H₁₂O₆ requires C, 65.39; H, 3.84%).

Methyl-7-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-6-carboxylate : 7-Hydroxy-4'-methoxyflavone-6-carboxylic acid (0.2 g.), methyl alcohol (5 ml.) and conc. sulphuric acid (2 drops) were refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hrs. and then poured with ice cold water when a product separated. It crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 190°. It neither gave any colour with ferric chloride solution nor dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution. However, it dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution. (Found : C, 67.41; H, 4.64. C₁₈H₁₄O₆ requires C, 67.51; H, 4.37%).

Methyl-7,4'-dimethoxyflavone-6-carboxylate : The above ester (0.5 g.) was refluxed in acetone with dimethyl sulphate (1.0 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate on a steam bath for 8 hrs. The product obtained on removal of acetone was crystallised from ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 208°.

The same product was obtained on simultaneous methylation and esterification of 7-hydroxy-4'-methoxyflavone-6-carboxylic acid with dimethyl sulphate in the presence of potassium carbonate in acetone solution. (Found : C, 63.65; H, 4.85. C₁₉H₁₆O₆ requires C, 64.11; H, 4.70%).

6-Methoxy-5-cyanoflavone : An intimate mixture of 6-methoxy-5-iodoflavone (3 g.), cuprous cyanide (1.78 g.) and copper sulphate (0.25 g.) was heated at 260–65° for 10 hrs. and then extracted with hot acetone. The product obtained on removal of acetone and extraction with acetic acid crystallised in colourless needles, m.p. 251°. (Found : C, 73.5; H, 4.00; N, C₁₇H₁₁O₃N requires C, 73.64; H, 4.00; N, 5.05%).

2-Acetyl-3-hydroxy-6-methoxybenzoic acid : 6-Methoxy-5-cyanoflavone (0.5 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (10%, 20 ml.) on a steam bath for 3 hrs. The product obtained on acidification was extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution. The above extract on acidification gave a product which crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 174°. Its alcoholic solution gave a deep brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 57.01; H, 4.88. C₁₀H₁₀O₅ requires C, 57.14; H, 4.76%). The above product (1.0 g.) when heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (4.0 g.) at 145–50° for 3 hrs. gave quinacetophenone.

The 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone of the above keto acid was prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene gave m.p. 265°. (Found : N, 14.22. C₁₆H₁₄O₈N₄ requires N, 14.35%).

Oxime of 7-hydroxy-8-acetylflavone : A mixture of 7-hydroxy-8-acetylflavone (0.5 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5 g.) and sodium hydroxide (10%, 2 ml.) was refluxed for 2 hr. The product obtained on acidification crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles (0.1 g.) m.p. 237°. (Found : C, 68.72; H, 4.36; N, 4.50. C₁₇H₁₃O₄N requires C, 69.14; H, 4.44; N, 4.74%).

7-Hydroxy-8-acetamidoflavone : The above oxime (1.0 g.) was added to well cooled phosphorus oxychloride (10 ml.) and the reaction mixture was heated at 70–80° for 5 mins, when the reaction mixture became dark brown in colour. It was then poured on ice. The product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 250°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 69.62; H, 4.72; N, 4.95. $C_{17}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 69.14; H, 4.44; N, 4.74%).

7-Hydroxy-8-aminoflavone : 7-Hydroxy-8-acetamidoflavone (0.5 g.) was refluxed with sulphuric acid (50%, 25 ml.) for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was then diluted with ice cold water and filtered. The filtrate on neutralization with ammonium hydroxide gave a product which crystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. 246°. Mixed m.p. with 7-hydroxy-8-aminoflavone as described below was not depressed. (Found : C, 71.20; H, 4.21; N, 5.26. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 71.14; H, 4.34; N, 5.53%).

7-Hydroxy-8-nitroflavone (1.0 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (2.0 ml.) and a solution of stannous chloride (2.0 g.) in glacial acetic acid added. The reaction mixture was heated on a steam bath for 1 hr. and then saturated with hydrogen chloride gas when the hydrochloride separated. It was filtered and redissolved in water and then neutralized with sodium bicarbonate solution when the free base separated.

Oxime of 7-hydroxy-8-benzoylflavone : It was prepared by refluxing 7-hydroxy-8-benzoylflavone (0.2 g.) in alcohol with a solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5 g.) and sodium hydroxide for 8 hrs. The product on working up as before crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles (0.1 g.), m.p. 262–63°. (Found : C, 73.79; H, 4.06; N, 3.77. $C_{16}H_{10}O_4N$ requires C, 73.97; H, 4.23; N, 3.92%).

7-Hydroxy-8-benzamidoflavone : The above oxime (1.0 g.) was heated with phosphorus oxychloride (10 ml.) on a steam bath for 10 mins. The product obtained crystallised from acetone, m.p. 267°. (Found : C, 73.79; H, 3.88. $C_{22}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 73.94; H, 3.92%; N, 3.92%).

7-Hydroxy-8-benzamidoflavone (0.5 g.) was hydrolysed with sulphuric acid as in the previous case when 7-hydroxy-8-aminoflavone was obtained.

Oxime of 7-hydroxy-8-formylflavone : Prepared according to the process described earlier, crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 273–4°. (Found : C, 67.97; H, 4.11; N, 5.15. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4N$ requires C, 68.33; H, 3.91; N, 4.98%).

The oxime (1.0 g.) on heating with phosphoryl chloride (10 ml.) on a steam bath for 10 mins. gave the known 7-hydroxy-8-cyanoflavone.

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